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Graphene-Interfaced Stretchable Sweat Patch for Multiplexed Electrochemical Monitoring of IL-6, Glucose, and Calcium Ions

Roomia Memon | Ali Tufani | Süleyman Çelik | Javed H. Niazi | Anjum Qureshi

Sabanci University Nanotechnology Research and Application Center, Orta Mah. Tuzla, Istanbul, Turkey

Correspondence: Javed H. Niazi (javed@sabanciuniv.edu) | Anjum Qureshi (anjum@sabanciuniv.edu)

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ABSTRACT

Wearable electrochemical sensors are rapidly advancing toward non-invasive health monitoring, but most devices remain limited to single-analyte detection or rely on rigid substrates with poor skin compatibility. Here, we report a fully integrated and flexible sweat patch featuring interdigitated graphene/gold microelectrodes and a microfluidic platform for multiplexed detection of interleukin-6 (IL-6), glucose, and calcium ions in microliter sweat volumes. Graphene nanostructures enhance charge transfer and enlarge the electroactive surface area, while biofunctionalization with antibodies, enzymes, and ion-selective membranes ensures analyte-specific recognition. The microfluidics module prevents evaporation and drives sweat through capillary forces, enabling stable signal acquisition. The device demonstrates dynamic ranges of 0.1–300 pg mL⁻¹ for IL-6, 10 μM–1 mM for glucose, and 0.25–3 mM for Ca²⁺, covering physiologically relevant levels in human sweat. Linear regression yielded high correlation coefficients ($R^2 > 0.97$) with limits of detection of 10 pg mL⁻¹ (IL-6), 6 μM (glucose), and 26 μM (Ca²⁺). Compared with recently reported wearable sweat sensors, our device uniquely integrates multiplexed detection of inflammatory, metabolic, and electrolyte biomarkers on a flexible sensor platform. This work demonstrates the potential of graphene-interfaced sweat patches for real-time, personalized health monitoring and future wireless, on-body clinical translation.

1 | Introduction

Wearable bioelectronics has revolutionized personalized healthcare by enabling continuous and non-invasive physiological monitoring, shifting the paradigm from episodic clinical testing to a more proactive approach [1–3]. While minimally invasive approaches such as microneedle-based continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems have achieved clinical success, they still suffer from drawbacks including discomfort, infection risk, and relatively high cost [4, 5]. A pivotal aspect of this technological evolution lies in the utilization of human sweat as a diagnostic medium. Sweat serves as an accessible source of complex biomarkers, including metabolites, electrolytes, and

proteins, which provide valuable insights into systemic health [6]. By monitoring these specific analytes, real-time insights into metabolic function, hydration levels, and immune responses can be gained. However, the transition from rigid laboratory sensors to flexible wearable platforms presents significant material and architectural challenges that need to be overcome to fully realize the potential of wearable bioelectronics in personalized healthcare [7].

Effective sweat management is another crucial parameter for reliable wearable sensing, as uncontrolled sweat evaporation risks analyte measurement accuracy. At the skin-sensor interface, evaporation causes fluid loss, imbalances local temperature and

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humidity, and compromises sensor performance [8–11]. This fluid loss alters biomarker concentration, preventing stable signal acquisition for precise physiological monitoring. To mitigate these risks, advanced wearable platforms integrate microfluidic modules designed to harvest and protect sweat samples. These modules use specialized reservoir geometries and μ -channel structures to ensure uniform analyte exposure at sensing sites while shielding samples from environmental evaporation. By maintaining stable wetting of electrodes and enabling controlled, low-volume sample delivery, these integrated systems ensure stable, reproducible, and reflective electrochemical signals of individual's physiological state [12].

Integrated platforms that combine inflammatory protein markers with metabolites and ions provide a comprehensive and holistic assessment of an individual's physiological state, encompassing immune activation, metabolic function, and electrolyte imbalance [3, 6, 13, 14]. Cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) are central indicators of infection, inflammation, and chronic disease, yet their incorporation into wearable devices remains largely unexplored. Achieving sensitive and selective detection of multiple analyte classes in microliter sweat volumes demands electrode materials with high electrochemical activity, large surface area, and compatibility with diverse biorecognition mechanisms [7, 12, 15–19].

Graphene is a leading material for wearable bioelectronics due to its exceptional electrical conductivity, specific surface area, and rapid electron-transfer characteristics [6, 20]. However, existing fabrication methods like laser-induced graphene and screen-printing face challenges, such as incomplete mechanical robustness, limited patterning resolution, and poor adhesion to soft substrates. While chemical vapor deposition (CVD) produces high-quality graphene, it is too complex and costly for scalable manufacturing. Recent advances in wearable bioelectronics have also explored organic electrochemical transistor (OECT)-based sensors for their signal amplification capabilities [21–23], but integrating these devices into flexible platforms with multiplexed biochemical sensing is challenging due to complexity and fabrication constraints. Therefore, there is a critical need for scalable and robust fabrication strategies that can integrate high-quality graphene into flexible electrode architectures with precise geometry, strong adhesion, and enhanced electrochemical performance.

In this paper, we report the development of a fully integrated and stretchable sweat patch featuring interdigitated graphene and gold microelectrodes for the multiplexed detection of IL-6, glucose, and calcium ions. The device is constructed on a flexible polyimide substrate which provides the necessary mechanical resilience for on skin applications while supporting a high signal-to-noise ratio required for sensitive measurements. The sensing platform consists of a 1×3 array of sensors where each working electrode utilizes a crescent shaped design incorporating 18 alternating gold and graphene microelectrodes. This interdigitated architecture significantly enhances the electroactive surface area and promotes efficient charge transfer for the detection of analytes in microliter sweat volumes.

A critical component of the device is the integrated microfluidic module fabricated from polydimethylsiloxane. This module

is engineered to harvest sweat directly from the skin and drive it through a network of microchannels using passive capillary forces, eliminating the need for external pumping systems. The design features specific reservoir geometries and serpentine channels to ensure uniform analyte exposure and mixing at the sensing sites while preventing sample evaporation, which is essential for stable signal acquisition.

The specificity of the multiplexed platform is achieved through precise biofunctionalization of the graphene interfaces. The electrodes are selectively modified with anti-IL-6 antibodies, glucose oxidase enzymes, and calcium ion selective membranes. This allows the patch to operate across wide dynamic ranges, specifically 0.1–300 pg per mL for IL-6, 10 μ M to 1 mM for glucose, and 0.25–3 mM for Ca^{2+} . These ranges effectively cover the physiologically relevant levels found in human sweat for both healthy and diseased states.

Furthermore, the sensor demonstrates remarkable mechanical resilience by maintaining electrochemical performance and structural integrity under repetitive stretching, bending, and twisting. Validation against gold standard assays ensured accuracy and reliability of the platform. By combining inflammatory, metabolic, and electrolyte monitoring on a single stretchable graphene platform, this study advances the potential for comprehensive real time health diagnostics and paves the way for future wireless and battery free wearable health systems.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Design of Micro/Nano-Structured Graphene Interfaced Electrode Sensor Arrays on a Flexible Substrate

This sensor patch is designed to contain arrays of interdigitated graphene/metal microelectrodes and a microfluidics system, which allows for monitoring of multiple analytes real-time from small sweat volumes (Figure 1a,b). The wearable and flexible multiplexed design carries three independent sensor arrays, each array was made of 18 ring-shaped graphene and gold alternating interdigitated (IDE) microelectrodes that function as working (W) electrode, which is flanked by a reference (R) and a counter (C) electrode, on to which sweat is dispensed from integrated microfluidics channel inlets. Two different design layouts of graphene/gold microelectrode sensors were fabricated using a combination of graphene coating and photolithography techniques (Scheme S1a,b). These layout designs were fabricated in; (a) alternating and (b) parallel pad connection orientations in sensor arrays on a patch for making convenient electrical contacts. Here, three arrays of electrochemical sensors enabled multiplexing of three distinct sweat analytes simultaneously. Interfacing of graphene with electronic sensor arrays promoted the charge transfer ability of sensors to capture sweat biomarkers more sensitively and specifically. The designed sensor patch is made of a flexible polyimide (PI), a polymeric film substrate, which carries dynamic charges with its chemical potential accompanied by those charge carriers from coated graphene. Such substrate not only provided flexibility and large interfacial area in between electrodes of sensor surface, but also facilitated

FIGURE 1 | (a) Schematic illustration of the flexible wearable sweat-sensing patch integrating an array of electrochemical sensors. The working electrodes are selectively biofunctionalized with specific recognition elements, including (i) anti-IL-6 antibodies, (ii) glucose oxidase (GOx), and (iii) Ca^{2+} ion-selective membrane, enabling multiplex detection of inflammatory, metabolic, and electrolyte biomarkers in biofluids such as sweat. (b) Enlarged schematic view of the microelectrode sensor architecture showing interdigitated gold and graphene microelectrodes forming the working electrode. The working electrode is flanked by a gold reference electrode (RE) and counter electrode (CE), enabling electrochemical detection of target biomarkers.

high signal-to-noise ratio, making it most desirable for a typical wearable device.

Each sensor in an array is assigned to generate a specific electrochemical signal with respect to a specific sweat biomarker. The specificity of sensor originates from the embedded specific receptor element bio-activated on working electrodes of sensor as shown in Figure 1a,b. The microfluidics channel drives sweat by capillary forces on to specific sensors pre-activated with bioreceptors (Figure S2a–d and Video S1). The microfluidic layout (Figure S2) was engineered to enable passive, capillary-driven sweat transport and controlled distribution across the sensing chambers. The device comprises a ~ 70 mm long channel network integrating sequential circular reservoirs (diameter ≈ 10.8 mm) interconnected by microchannels with widths ranging from 230 to 500 μm . These dimensions were selected to balance capil-

lary pressure and hydraulic resistance, ensuring spontaneous filling while preventing abrupt fluid overflow. Serpentine channel segments (~ 350 μm width) were incorporated to increase flow resistance and stabilize the transport rate, thereby enabling uniform analyte exposure at each sensing site. The inlet–outlet configuration promotes unidirectional flow and minimizes back-diffusion, while the chamber geometry ensures sufficient sample retention for reliable electrochemical measurements. This design allows consistent fluid handling without the need for external pumping systems. These sensors specifically capture three different model sweat analytes, such as (i) a sweat cytokine, interleukin-6 (IL-6), (ii) sweat glucose, and (iii) sweat Ca^{2+} ions in a multiplexed format on a single platform (Figure 2a–d).

The signal transduction mechanism of wearable sensor patch is based on changes in electrochemical properties, which occur

FIGURE 2 | (a) Block diagram depicting the operational concept of the potentiostat and signal readout circuitry while managing an electrochemical sensor. (b) A cyclic voltammogram (i) showing current vs. applied potential, with anodic (oxidation) and cathodic (reduction) peaks, with peak currents I_{pa} , I_{pc} and potentials E_{pa} , E_{pc} characterize the redox couple and its reversibility. (ii, iii) Photographs showing a sensor patch on the skin is connected to an external portable potentiostat (EmStat Pico module with inbuilt analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog converter) and a smartphone App that measures the specific signal from bio-activated sensors and the change in the current/potential signal specific to the captured sweat analyte is displayed on a smartphone. (c) Photograph of a fully integrated, flexible, and wearable sensor patch attached on the arm skin. Each patch is made of an array of 3 sensors, each sensor is made of a working interdigitated alternating graphene and metal microelectrodes (WE) pre-activated with bioreceptors, a reference (RE) and a counter electrode (RE), respectively, and (d) A schematic depiction of a sweat gland on a skin section, with a sensor patch closely contacting the sweat excreted from a sweat pore, and the sweat being autonomously drawn through the sensor's inlet pad via capillary action.

due to change in modulation of graphene's carrier properties combined with protein/metabolite/ions (sweat analytes) upon interaction with its specific receptor elements (antibodies/enzyme/selective membrane) present on the sensor patch. This method is based on low power consumption and provides high precision current/potential signal measurements. The independent and selective operation of individual sensors in 3-arrays is preserved during multi-analyte and/or multi-modal capabilities by employing highly specific surface bio-/chemistries and electrically decoupling the operating conditions of each sensor interface. Therefore, specific electrochemical signal originating from each sensor on arrays provided a specific signature, which enables discriminating the biomarker type, as well as determining their concentration ratios, simply by a signal-readout and signal processing based on portable-handheld unit of a potentiostat equipped with a simple profiling algorithm and Bluetooth (Figure 2a–d). The dynamic range of detection established in this study (discussed in Section 2.4) using the wearable sensor patch for IL-6 = 0.1–300 pg/mL (cover typical IL-6 concentration in human sweat), glucose = 10 μ M–1 mM (covers the typical

range found in human sweat for hypoglycemic, hyperglycemic, and healthy individuals) Ca^{2+} ion = 0.1–3 mM (cover range typically found in human body fluids, including sweat sample) and sufficient to diagnose the disease risk.

2.2 | Patterning of Micro/Nano-Structured Graphene Electrode Sensor Arrays on Graphene Coated Flexible PI Film and Testing Mechanical Integrity

The wearable graphene interfaced electrochemical sensor arrays patch fabrication was carried out using standard photolithography process on flexible PI substrates using following steps.

2.2.1 Physico-chemical characterization of graphene electrodes on polyimide (PI)

Graphene coated on flexible polymeric PI substrate was fabricated as described in the Experimental Section. The

graphene-coated film substrate was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) analysis, and scanning electron microscopic (SEM) examinations (Figure 3a–f). XRD-patterns of bare PI film, graphene nanoplatelets and graphene coated PI substrate are shown in Figure 3a. A high-intense diffraction peak at $2\theta = 25.6^\circ$ and tiny peaks at 43.59° , 53.0° , and 63.9° was identified for PI semi-crystalline structure (Figure 3a). XRD-pattern for pure graphene showed a single highly intense diffraction peak found at 26.15° as 2θ , with a 3.35 \AA inter-spacing. This peak corresponds to the crystalline plane (002) of the graphene nanoplatelet. Peaks found at 42.69° , 44.53° , and 55.00° as 2θ were assigned to the (100), (101), and (004) planes, respectively, which are consistent to a previous study [24]. The XRD patterns of graphene coated PI substrate exhibited merging of diffraction peaks, indicating a mixture of diffraction peaks from both PI and pure graphene within the $2\theta = 20^\circ\text{--}30^\circ$ (25.6° , 26.15°). Additional peaks were observed at $2\theta = 5^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$ including smaller peaks at 43.59° , 44.53° , and 63.70° , corresponding to (002), (100), and (101), respectively (Figure 3a). These results indicate the partial crystallinity of pure graphene and confirm the successful coating of graphene on PI substrate. The intensity of the diffraction pattern from PI substrate is lower than that of coated graphene due to the interference of the PI substrate in the overall XRD data.

Figure 3b displays the Raman spectra of PI, graphene, and graphene-coated PI. The Raman spectra of graphene exhibited D, G, and 2D bands at 1341 , 1570 , and 2685 cm^{-1} , respectively. The low intense D band signifies the presence of hybridized carbon atoms with few defects, while the high-intensity G band corresponds to the vibrations of the sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms in the basal graphene plane. In the Raman spectra of graphene coated PI substrate, we observed both the D and G bands on PI surface, and the Raman signal from the graphene nanoplatelets encapsulated within PI substrate were easily detectable. Interestingly, the G band of the graphene-coated PI showed a slight shift from 1570 to 1575 cm^{-1} compared to the G band of pure graphene. Additionally, the G band of graphene-coated PI overlapped with the other two bands of PI located at 1510 and 1612 cm^{-1} . These findings demonstrated the successful coating of graphene nanoplatelets on PI substrate. TGA analysis of cleaned PI substrate and graphene-coated PI sensor substrates, as shown in Figure 3c. The results revealed that the residual weight of graphene coated PI was higher than that of control uncoated PI substrate. This increase in residual weight indicates that graphene confers higher thermal stability to the coated PI substrate. This aligns with the well-known property of graphene being thermally stable and resistant to decomposition at high temperatures [25]. Hence, the graphene coated PI substrate achieved enhanced thermal stability which enabled thermal treatment (baking) and annealing processes during photolithography patterning of microelectrodes.

Structural features, durability, and stability of graphene coated polymeric substrate was carried out by SEM imaging before and after several washing cycles (25–50) (Figure 3d–f). For this, each $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ graphene coated substrate was washed with a 200 mL of SDBS detergent (0.37%) without optical brightener (WOB) solution. SEM images of graphene coated PI substrate showed partial detachment of non-adhered graphene after 50 cycles of washing. SEM images revealed that graphene coated PI substrate could resist washing for 50 cycles. After successful

confirmation of the durability and stability, the graphene coated polymeric substrate was subjected to fabrication of graphene-interfaced microelectrodes by photolithography method in the following section.

2.2.2 Patterning of micro/nano-structured graphene electrode sensor arrays on graphene-coated flexible PI film and testing mechanical integrity.

Fabrication of gold interdigitated microelectrodes on graphene coated flexible polymeric film substrates from above Section, was carried out using standard photolithography technique toward developing sensor patches. To interpret the changes in sensor responses, the micro-nano-electrodes were also patterned on bare polymeric substrates without graphene, serving as control sensors. The fabricated micro/nano-structured graphene-interfaced electrochemical sensor on a flexible polymeric substrate was characterized by optical and SEM imaging (Figure 3g–m). The optical images of flexible sensor patch with control gold microelectrodes (without graphene) and graphene interfaced sensor patch are shown in Figure 3g–j. The control sensor clearly showed interdigitated rings on a smooth polymeric film surface without graphene in between the microelectrodes. Whereas the graphene interfaced electrochemical flexible sensor showed rough surface of the film between the gold microelectrodes (Figure 3i–j). The dimension of each microelectrode (gold/graphene) measured was $\leq 40\text{--}60 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ that are separated by $40 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ within a sensor area of $\sim 7 \times 10 \text{ mm}$. The SEM images of graphene-interfaced electrochemical sensor patch are shown in Figure 3k–m. In the fabricated design of sensor arrays, the nano-structured graphene (nanosized platelets) homogeneously distributed in between the gold interdigitated (GID) microelectrode arrays (Figure 3l). A photograph of sensor patch showing an array of three sensors on flexible PI film is shown in Figure 3n. Each sensor patch consists of arrays of three working gold/graphene interdigitated electrode arrays with respective reference and counter electrodes on a single platform for electrochemical biosensing of multiple sweat biomarkers. The electrochemical performance of fabricated graphene interfaced electrochemical sensor patch and control gold electrode interfaced sensor (without graphene) patch was tested by recording their cyclic voltammogram (CV) responses in $5 \text{ mM K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ as electron mediator ($\text{pH} = 7.4$) with a sweep potential from -0.4 to $+0.2 \text{ V}$ at a scan rate of 50 mV/s (Figure S3). The graphene interfaced electrochemical flexible sensor patch exhibited increased current response as compared with control sensor. The response of the sensor clearly showed fast electron transfer kinetics which is associated with enhanced conductivity and surface area of graphene nanostructured electrodes.

The mechanical resilience of wearable graphene sensor arrays on a flexible PI patch was tested against mechanical strains (Figure 3o–t, Video S3, and Figure S4). The continuous applied mechanical stress was monitored through stretching, relaxing, bending, and twisting, as shown in photographs (Figure 3o–t and Video S3). Despite of the above mechanical strains and in combination of different stresses applied on flexible graphene sensor patch, the sensor patch tended to preserve its mechanical integrity and flexibility. Further, the electrochemical performance of fabricated wearable graphene sensor patch was also tested for 15 repetitive cycles (Figure S4). The results showed a stable CV response despite of repetitive cycles and it retained 92%–95% of its

FIGURE 3 | Characterization of polyimide film substrate (PI) that was coated with graphene. (a) XRD patterns, and (b) Raman spectra of PI substrate, pure graphene, and graphene-coated PI substrate, respectively. (c) Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) analysis of PI substrate and graphene coated PI substrate, respectively. (d) Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) images of graphene coated PI substrate; (e) after 25 cycles of washings, and (f) after 50 cycles of washings, respectively. Optical images of; (g,h) control gold interdigitated electrode arrays sensor on flexible polyimide substrate without graphene. (i,j) Single sensor showing graphene-interfaced, gold microelectrode arrays on flexible polyimide substrate. (k–m) SEM images of graphene-interfaced sensor electrodes on flexible polyimide substrate shown at higher magnifications (50–100X). Graphene nanostructures (100–200 nm) forming electrodes ($\leq 40\text{--}60\ \mu\text{m}$ in width) that were interfaced between gold interdigitated microelectrodes ($40\ \mu\text{m}$) for each sensor $\sim 7 \times 10\ \text{mm}$ area). (n) A photograph showing graphene-interfaced sensor arrays on flexible PI patch (o–t and Video S2). The mechanical resilience of gold/graphene sensor arrays on flexible PI patch against the applied mechanical strains, such as by stretching, relaxing, bending, and twisting as see in the images.

initial signal, and therefore the fabricated graphene sensor patch found to be suitable for repetitively measuring the current signals.

2.2.3 Bio-functionalization of sensor patch with specific chemical/bioreceptor to sweat biomarker and characterization

The chemical and bioactivation of graphene sensor arrays was confirmed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis after bio-functionalization of specific targeted receptor element, such as IL-6 antibodies probe, IgG monoclonal antibody specific to glucose oxidase enzyme and Ca^{2+} -ion selective membrane (Ca-ISM) element (Figure S5a–c).

The FTIR spectra of flexible PI substrate showed the main five spectral regions of polyimide C–C skeletal modes, such as C–N–C stretching, C–H, carbonyl groups (C=O), and N–H stretching [26] (Figure S5). The C–N–C vibration featured at 710–1000 cm^{-1} , while CH_2 groups emerged between 1000 and 1500 cm^{-1} and carbonyl groups (C=O) were observed between 1540 and 1720 cm^{-1} . The C–H stretching vibration of methylene groups were observed at 2865 and 2935 cm^{-1} , while amide group (N–H) appeared at 3311 cm^{-1} . The graphene interfaced flexible sensor showed C–O and C=O groups of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) at 1070 and 1760 cm^{-1} , respectively [27].

IL-6 antibody coupling on PASE functionalized graphene interfaced sensor surface was confirmed by the appearance of two new bands of amide-II and amide-I at 1510 and 1658 cm^{-1} , respectively (Figure S5a). The first type is the characteristic amide bands that emerged in the region between 1200 and 1700 cm^{-1} and these bands corresponded to linking segment to amino acids [28]. The second type is associated with IL-6 antibody functionalized on graphene interfaced sensor surface, where amide-II at 1510 cm^{-1} corresponded to bending vibration of the N–H bond of the amide group and N–C stretching and C=O bending. The amide-I group emerged at 1658 cm^{-1} that corresponds to C=O stretching mode of amide with contribution of C–C–N and C–N stretching vibrations. The O–H stretching band is derived from the N–H₂ bond that appeared at 3380 cm^{-1} . The emergence of these characteristics of IL-6 antibody functionalized on graphene interfaced sensor clearly showed coverage of C=O and N–H bonds originating from protein functional groups and confirmed the immobilization of IL-6 specific antibodies on the graphene interfaced sensor surface.

Glucose oxidase coupling on IgG antibody (specific to glucose oxidase) functionalized graphene sensor surface was confirmed by the appearance of two new bands of amide II and amide I at 1520 and 1640 cm^{-1} , respectively (Figure S5b). The FTIR spectra of glucose oxidase (GOx) immobilized on flexible graphene sensor surface showed strong N–H stretching at 3280 cm^{-1} , while the characteristic peaks of N–H in plane bending and C–N stretching modes of the polypeptide chains of glucose oxidase are assigned at 1640 cm^{-1} (amide-I) and amide-II assigned at 1520 cm^{-1} , respectively [29]. The slight shift of amide-I and amide-II modes in the glucose oxidase functionalized sensor surface in comparison with only IgG antibody surface was attributed to the intermolecular interaction between glucose oxidase enzyme and IgG antibody, which favor the stability of glucose oxidase on the graphene interfaced sensor surface.

The FTIR spectra of surface modified graphene interfaced electrode with Ca-ISM cocktail (Figure S5c). The calcium ionophore bands were observed at 3321 cm^{-1} (N–H, secondary amine), 2925 cm^{-1} (O–H stretching), 1647 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching), and 1000 cm^{-1} (C–O stretching). The KTFPB, o-NPOE, and PVC related bands were observed at 2867 cm^{-1} (CH_2 stretching), 1620 cm^{-1} and 1540 cm^{-1} (N–H primary amine), 1456 cm^{-1} (C–C stretching), and 1000 cm^{-1} (C–Cl stretching). The presence of these functional groups confirmed the functionalization of Ca-ISM sensor electrode.

2.2.4 Stability of the sensor and on-artificial skin analysis of sensor patch for variation in pH and temperature during glucose sensing

The sensor patches pre-activated with receptors for IL6, glucose oxidase, or Ca^{2+} -specific membrane was tested with synthetic sweat samples for stability and reproducibility in its CV response signals (Figure S6a–i). After 6 successive cycles of measurements, the sensor responses against specific concentration of each of the analytes tested (e.g., 0 pg IL-6, 0.4 mM glucose, and 0.75 mM Ca^{2+}) was recorded that showed consistent and reproducible signals (Figure S6a,d,g). Each of these sensors was further subjected to testing after 7-days of storage at standard 4°C temperature (Figure S6b,e,h). We observed that storage conditions did not affect the sensor patch responses indicating that the sensors have shelf-life of at least over a week under ideal 4°C storage conditions. Preliminary ambient-condition storage tests indicated that the sensor retained stable performance for at least 2 weeks at room temperature. Further, fabrication processes, such as batch-to-batch variations in fabricated sensor patch responses were tested to ascertain for any unintended sensor patch behavior. Here, three independent sensor patches fabricated from three different batches were tested in triplicates for their electrochemical responses (designated as S1~S3) under optimized conditions as described above with each type of sensors against IL-6, glucose, and Ca^{2+} in synthetic sweat sample, respectively. The sensor patch exhibited consistent current (ΔI) responses for IL-6 and glucose, respectively. However, batch-to-batch variation in the sensor responses was prone to occur with Ca^{2+} ion sweat sensors, mostly due to the inconsistent thickness of the ion-membrane layer formed on sensors during pre-activation process, which can be acceptable because this variation occurred whose percent relative standard deviation (%RSD) was less than 10%.

The sensor patch's response to pH and temperature was tested using model sensors functionalized with specific receptor elements, such as anti-glucose oxidase. These sensors were tested on an artificial skin setup, equipped with an absorbent pad to facilitate the rapid access of synthetic sweat to the sensor surface. It is to be noted that the sweat pH can vary substantially under physiological conditions, particularly during intense exercise, and that this can influence the response of enzyme-based glucose sensors. In the present study, however, the glucose sensor was systematically evaluated within the pH range of 6.4–7.4 (Figure S7b), which was selected to represent the near-neutral physiological window most relevant to resting to moderate perspiration conditions and to assess sensor stability under controlled conditions. The resulting sensor responses measured at additional controlled conditions, such as at constant 0.1 mM glucose at +0.1 V, while varying the temperature and pH. Figure S7a illustrates the sensors' moderate temperature

dependence, with the response reaching a minimum at 30°C and increasing at both lower (25°C) and higher (35°C) temperatures. Similarly, Figure S7b demonstrates a non-linear dependence on pH, with the lowest response observed at pH 7.0 and higher current responses at pH 6.4 and pH 7.4. These V-shaped trends suggest that the sensor exhibits some sensitivity to the immediate physicochemical environment. However, the observed variations remain within a range that allows for predictable correction, thereby supporting reliable measurements across normal physiologically relevant temperatures (25°C–30°C) and pH values (6.4–7.4) (Figure S7a,b). Together, these results demonstrate that the fabricated flexible sensor patches exhibit predictable and reliable current responses, supporting their suitability for electrochemical sweat biomarker detection and real-time glucose monitoring applications. To further improve on-body applicability, future work will focus on extending the operational pH window, including evaluation under acidic sweat conditions and integration of pH-compensation or co-calibration strategies to improve quantitative robustness.

2.3 | Wearable Sensor Patch—Integration of Microfluidics with Sensors and Testing

The microfluidic module was designed to match the geometric specifications of the fabricated electrochemical sensor patch (Figure S2). Figure 4a–g presents images of the fabricated microfluidic module, illustrating its alignment with the geometry and dimensions of the flexible electrochemical sensor arrays.

The microfluidics platform module was fabricated using a SU-8 template and silicone (PDMS) material that is optimized for liquid:water (1 g/cm³)/air for delivering the sample in micro/nano liter volumes through the channels and distribute among the test sensor chambers assigned to detecting a specific biomarker (Figure 4a). The designed microfluidic module does not require external pump as the capillary-forces/pressure drives the liquid from an inlet pad through a laminar flow with a contact angle for interface material-liquid >90°. The unreacted molecules/fluid migrate toward the outlet with a directional flow due to varying channel diameters. Here, large channel inlet size (500 μm) with smaller outlet channels (230 μm) allow sample toward the outlet passing through the reaction chambers where the sensors are embedded (Figure 4a–g). The microfluidic design features and fabricated structures are shown in Figure 4a–d. The reservoir volume can hold up to 15–30 μL sample with the above diameters and operates at pressure ~190 Pa/reservoir. The microfluidic inlet was designed with a relatively larger collection region to facilitate efficient sweat harvesting from the skin surface and to accommodate intermittent non-uniform sweat generation under low sweat-rate conditions. This inlet acts as a temporary collection and buffering zone, allowing sweat to coalesce before being transported into the sensing chamber via capillary forces. Although this geometry may introduce modest dead volume, it was selected to promote directional flow from the larger inlet reservoir into the narrower downstream microchannels, improve sample acquisition reliability, and maintain stable wetting of the sensing electrodes with only ~10–30 μL of sweat. The larger inlet reservoir also enables gentle manual (thumb) assistance, if needed, to drive sweat toward the sensing region and sustain analyte sensor-contact. In future iterations, we will aim to reduce

inlet dead volume and shorten the transport path to further improve response time and on-body performance under low sweat-rate conditions. The microfluidics platform is integrated with graphene sensor arrays patch (bio-activated) by physical bonding during the assembly process and it is designed to contain 3 test chambers for simultaneous and multiplexed detection of 3 analytes, or a combination of 2 analytes and 1 control sample for error analysis on a single sensor patch with a larger inlet and small outlet.

The sweat flow through the microfluidic channels on the sensors was first tested using physiologically relevant solution (PBS pH 7.4) at different flow rates (15–35 μL/min). This allowed understanding the risks of leakage, microfluidics channel clogging with bubbles, molecules, or salts form PBS through micro channels under controlled conditions using a syringe pump (Video S1). Figure S8 shows the measured flow-rate and the time taken to saturate with fluid in the μchannels that was dependent on time. The loss of fluid sample imbalances optimal local temperature and relative humidity in sensor patch system that may affect the overall sensor patch system performance. Therefore, the effect of local temperature and rate of evaporation was tested by passing a rhodamine dye fluid into the microfluidic system that was placed at different temperatures (25°C–40°C) and relative humidity (RH%) over specific time intervals as shown in Figure 4h–l. The degree of evaporation of fluid in the microfluidic channel was determined by observing for any shift in the level of a colored dye in the channels over a specific time interval (0–1 h). It was observed that there was no significant loss of fluid in the microfluidics system at room temperature. However, partial fluid loss (approximately 2–5 μL) was observed only when the temperature increased above 40°C (Figure 4j). Further, the fully integrated sensors with microfluidic platform were analyzed for determining the rate of evaporation of dyed fluid as shown in Figure 4h–l. These experiments demonstrated that there was no significant dye fluid evaporation occurred at different time intervals tested at varying room temperature to physiologically relevant temperatures (25°C–40°C), suggesting that the microfluidic integrated sensor patch meets the requirement for testing with sweat samples.

2.4 | Fully-Integrated Electrochemical Sensing Patch Against Targeted Sweat Biomarkers and Validation

The flexible graphene-interfaced IL-6 sweat sensor exhibited a concentration-dependent response to applied electric potentials ranging from –0.1 to +0.1 V (refer to Figure 5a). Values extrapolated from cyclic voltammogram at a specific potential V displayed a linear curve demonstrating the increasing signal responses of sensor patch to increasing levels of IL-6 in sweat (Figure 5b). These findings highlight the remarkably sensitive cyclic voltammetry (CV) signals originating from the sensors patch, specifically in relation to IL-6 concentrations within the range of 0.1 and 300 pg/mL (typical IL-6 concentration in human sweat). The linear response of IL-6 sweat sensor patch with increasing concentration of 0.1–300 pg/mL, and this range is a representative of typical IL-6 concentrations found in human sweat. The limit-of-detection (LoD) as determined from the linear relationship was 10 pg/mL. The sweat sensor patch showed

FIGURE 4 | (a) Photographs of fabricated microfluidic patch module designed to fit according to the specifications of flexible electrochemical sensor arrays. Each microfluidic module consists of 3 test chambers to accommodate three sensors in an array that are connected each other with a microchannel to deliver micro-volumes of the samples. (b–d) Images of microchannels taken from an optical microscope at 100X magnification from the microfluidic platform module. (e–g) Photographs showing fabricated microfluidic module before and after assembly and integration with flexible wearable sensor arrays on artificial skin. (h–k) Images of sections of the microfluidic module showing dyed fluid (PBS solution, pH 7.4 dyed with rhodamine G250) used to track the reduction in its movement using a ruler (shown in the images) due to possible evaporation at different temperatures (indicated as column titles) and relative humidity (indicated as row titles). (l) A photograph showing a fully integrated microfluidic device with electrochemical sensor patch filled with tracker dye from an inlet reservoir pad.

selective or discerning response to IL-6 in presence of other chemically and biologically relevant compounds in sweat, such as glucose and BSA (Figure 5c).

Similarly, the electrochemical signals were acquired from interdigitated electrodes integrated with graphene and immobilized with GOx (glucose oxidase) that served as a glucose sweat sensor patch (Figure 5d–f). These sensor patch responded to varying glucose concentrations spanning 10 μM to 1 mM. The selected glucose concentration range effectively encompasses levels typically observed in human sweat, covering hypoglycemic, hyperglycemic, and healthy ranges. The recorded monitoring responses of sweat patch for glucose exhibits a linear relationship characterized by an incremental change in sensor response signal until reaching to a saturation point at 1 mM glucose (Figure 5d,e).

Employing linear regression analysis, the LoD extrapolated from the data was determined to be 6 μM glucose with high linearity ($R^2 = 0.97$). The flexible sensor patch underscores the versatile capability to discriminate glucose (Glu) from other prominent bio/chemical compounds that may be present in sweat, such as uric acid (UA), as well as a structurally analogous compound, fructose (FRA) (Figure 5f).

The electrochemical responses to Ca^{2+} ions in synthetic sweat using sweat sensor patch preactivated with Ca-ISM are shown in Figure 5g–i. The electrochemical signals from the sensor patch against varying concentrations of Ca^{2+} ions ranging from 0.25 to 3 mM, was measured at applied potentials from -0.1 to $+0.1$ V (Figure 5g–i). The tested Ca^{2+} ion levels were within the normal range for human body fluids, including sweat. The

FIGURE 5 | (a) Cyclic voltammogram (CV) response of graphene electrochemical sensor immobilized with anti-IL6 antibodies was monitored against varying concentrations of IL-6 sweat biomarker at applied electric potential of -0.1 to $+0.1$ V, (b) the linear curve of IL-6 sweat sensor patch at different concentrations of IL-6 sweat biomarker and (c) CV response of IL-6 sweat sensor patch in the presence of chemical and biologically relevant species of sweat, such as glucose and BSA. (d) CV response of graphene electrochemical sensor arrays immobilized with Glucose oxidase (GOx) monitored against varying concentrations of glucose at applied potential of -0.1 to $+0.1$ V, (e) the linear response curve from sensor patch against different concentrations of glucose in synthetic sweat and (f) CV response from glucose sweat sensor patch in presence of relevant common bio/chemical species in sweat. (g) CV responses of graphene electrochemical sensor functionalized with Ca^{2+} -ion selective membrane. Here, the sensors were monitored varying concentrations of Ca^{2+} ions against applied potential of -0.1 to $+0.1$ V. (h) Linear response curve obtained from Ca^{2+} ion sensor patch incubated with synthetic sweat sample containing different concentrations of Ca^{2+} ions. (i) CV response from Ca^{2+} ion sweat sensor patch tested in the presence of relevant common bio/chemical species of sweat.

linear calibration curve demonstrates concentration-dependent increasing signals that correspond to the Ca^{2+} ions present in the test samples (Figure 5g,h). The LoD as calculated from the linear regression analysis was found to be $26 \mu\text{M}$ of Ca^{2+} ions (with $R^2 = 0.97$). The selective response of the Ca^{2+} ion sensor patch to Ca^{2+} ions, even in the presence of the other common sweat ion species, such as Mg^{2+} and K^+ (Figure 5h). The outcomes derived from the responses of the sensor patch distinctly demonstrate the establishment of minimum detectable or interaction levels for sweat biomarkers on the wearable sensor patch when operating under optimized conditions. However, the evaluated selectivity of

the IL 6, glucose, and Ca^{2+} sensors against common chemical and biological constituents of sweat, including glucose, electrolytes, and a control protein (BSA), as shown in Figure 5c,f,i yielded minor background signals from interferences, these responses remained substantially lower than the electrochemical changes elicited by the target analytes, confirming acceptable selectivity of the sensing layers. The small variations likely arise from non-specific electrochemical interactions inherent to complex biofluid matrices. Importantly, the dominant response is originated from the specific antibody, enzyme, or ion selective membrane interactions, demonstrating that the platform reliably distinguishes

target biomarkers from common sweat components. This selectivity of the sensing platform arises from the specific molecular recognition mechanisms employed for each analyte, including antibody–antigen binding for IL-6, enzymatic catalysis by glucose oxidase for glucose detection, and ion-selective membrane transport for Ca^{2+} sensing. The modest interference effects are expected in practical sweat based electrochemical sensing and they can be mitigated through calibration, antifouling strategies, and algorithmic compensation in future device iterations. Our results, however, support the feasibility of the patch for real-time, on-body trend monitoring of IL-6, glucose, and Ca^{2+} in physiologically relevant conditions. Future optimizations will further enhance its performance for more precise quantitative applications.

Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of recent wearable sweat sensors which not only include substrate format, target analytes, dynamic range, and LoD, but also practical performance metrics such as response time, storage stability, and multiplexing capability reported in the literature. A majority of wearable sweat sensors primarily focus on metabolites and/or electrolytes, while the present study uniquely combines sensing of cytokine (IL-6), metabolic (glucose), and ions (Ca^{2+}) within a single flexible sensor patch embedded with graphene/gold interdigitated microelectrodes and a microfluidics module. The device exhibits physiologically relevant detection ranges with low LoDs, a response time of approximately 5 min, and preliminary ambient-condition stability of at least 2 weeks, demonstrating competitive analytical and practical performance relative to recently reported platforms (Table 1). Importantly, the inclusion of IL-6 alongside glucose and Ca^{2+} extends the sensing scope beyond conventional sweat analyte panels and highlights the potential of this platform for more comprehensive physiological and inflammation-related monitoring.

Sensor patch assay validation was carried out with gold standard assays such as commercial glucometer for validating glucose response and determining Ca^{2+} ions using Fluo-4 Direct Calcium Assay Kit as gold standard method. Here, same synthetic sweat sample aliquots spiked with known concentrations and acceptable ranges of a specific sweat, glucose (10 μM –1 mM) and Ca^{2+} ions (0.25–1.5 mM) used for testing sensor patch was applied for validation.

The synthetic sweat samples containing different concentrations of spiked IL-6 protein (0.1–300 pg/mL), glucose (10 μM –1 mM), and Ca^{2+} ions (0.25–1.5 mM) were tested using standard assay, and the results of these assays were compared with biosensor patch device responses. The linear regression data were obtained from spiked IL-6 protein, glucose, and Ca^{2+} ions in synthetic sweat (Figure S9a–c). These linear responses demonstrated that the biosensor patch signals were comparable to standard in vitro assays. The sensor patch response showed consistent values for IL-6 protein that were comparable to the IL-6 protein levels determined using gold standard IL-6 ELISA tests (Figure S9a). The flexible biosensor patch device responses against micro molar (μM) range levels of glucose, however commercial glucose meter responded from 0.6 mM (millimolar range) of glucose levels (Figure S9b). This clearly indicated that the developed flexible biosensor patch is sensitive toward the detection of μM levels of glucose in sweat. The commercial glucose meter is designed

to detect the glucose levels in blood, where blood glucose is present in millimolar levels and therefore commercial glucose sensor (glucometer) did not respond to μM levels of glucose in sweat. Similarly, gold standard assay results for the detection of Ca^{2+} ions (0.25–1.5 mM) were comparable with biosensor patch device responses (Figure S9c). It was observed that the higher levels of Ca^{2+} ions (above 1 mM), the gold standard assay response was saturated, and it is challenging to accurately quantify possibly due to the handling of reaction mixture and reaction time and environmental conditions. We noticed that the quantitative analysis of sweat biomarkers in synthetic sweat using the developed flexible biosensor patch device was more suitable, rapid, sensitive, and generate distinguish signal compared to the standard assays (Table 2), and gold standard assays lack in options for detecting lower levels of sweat biomarker signal (glucose) in given settings.

The multiplexed sensing capability of the proposed platform enables several application scenarios that are difficult to achieve using single-analyte wearable sensors. For instance, simultaneous monitoring of IL-6, glucose, and Ca^{2+} may provide valuable insight into physiological responses during prolonged physical activity or metabolic stress. Exercise-induced inflammation is often associated with elevated cytokine levels, such as IL-6, while glucose concentration reflects metabolic energy consumption and Ca^{2+} levels are linked to electrolyte balance and muscle function. Therefore, concurrent tracking of these biomarkers may enable more comprehensive assessment of fatigue, hydration status, and inflammatory responses in athletes, military personnel, or individuals undergoing intensive physical activity. In addition, elevated IL-6 levels combined with metabolic fluctuations may serve as early indicators of systemic inflammation or infection. By integrating inflammatory, metabolic, and electrolyte biomarkers within a single stretchable sensing platform, the proposed device provides a more holistic approach to physiological monitoring compared to conventional wearable sensors that typically focus on a single analyte.

3 | Conclusion

In summary, this research demonstrates a fully integrated, flexible sweat patch capable of multiplexed, non-invasive monitoring of inflammatory, metabolic, and electrolyte biomarkers. By using a graphene interfaced interdigitated microelectrode architecture on a flexible polyimide substrate, the platform achieves high sensitivity and selectivity for IL-6, glucose, and Ca^{2+} across physiologically relevant ranges. The inclusion of a passive microfluidic module is critical to device performance, enabling autonomous sweat harvesting and transport through capillary forces while minimizing sample evaporation and supporting stable signal acquisition.

The sensor shows high linearity and low limits of detection, with performance comparable to established gold standard assays such as ELISA and commercial glucometers. It also exhibits strong mechanical resilience, retaining structural integrity and electrochemical performance under repeated stretching, bending, and twisting. By simultaneously tracking these three analyte classes, the device offers a holistic view of an individual's physiological

TABLE 1 | Comparative summary of recent wearable sweat sensors highlighting substrates, analytes, dynamic/LoD ranges, and multiplexing capabilities.

Device (Year)	Substrate/format	Analytes (example)	Reported dynamic range/LoD (as reported)	Response time	Stability	Multiplexing	Notes/strength (key citation)
This work (Revised)	Flexible PI patch; graphene/gold IDEs + capillary microfluidics	IL-6; Glucose; Ca ²⁺	IL-6: 0.1–300 pg mL ⁻¹ (LoD 10 pg mL ⁻¹); Glucose: 10 μM–1 mM (LoD 6 μM); Ca ²⁺ : 0.25–3 mM (LoD 26 μM)	5 min	At least 2 weeks	Yes (3 analytes)	Multiplexed IL-6 + metabolic + ionic sensing on single graphene IDE patch (this work)
Gao et al., Nature (2016)	Flexible patch with printed electrochemical sensors + ICs	Glucose, Lactate, Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Temperature	Reported physiologically relevant ranges for glucose 0–200 μM, lactate 0–200 μM, Na ⁺ 10–160 mM, K ⁺ 1–32 mM	Real-time	At least 4 weeks	Yes	Fully integrated wireless multiplexed patch [8]
Cheng et al., Microsystems & Nanoeng. (2023)	Paper-based origami microfluidic patch	Glucose, Lactate, Uric acid, Mg ²⁺ , pH, Cortisol	Sensitive for physiological sweat ranges (cortisol- 0.1 pM–5 μM)	10–15 min	NA	Yes	Low-cost, dual-signal readout (colorimetric + electrochemical) [30]
Chu et al., Biosensors & Bioelectronics (2023)	Textile/fabric integrated aptamer-CNT/graphene fibers	IL-6 (cytokine)	Sensitive IL-6 detection reported (1–100 ng/mL, LoD 0.28 pg/mL)	Real-time	1 week	Single cytokine (IL-6) demonstrated	Demonstrates feasibility of wearable cytokine (IL-6) monitoring [31]
Commercial/Translational (AWARE; 2024)	Wearable inflammation-tracking patch	Inflammatory markers (incl. cytokines)	Reported clinical tracking of inflammation markers CRP 525–1175 pg/mL and IL-6 0.45–3.14 pg/mL	Real-time	4 days	Yes	Translational devices tracking inflammation from sweat [32]

TABLE 2 | Summary of detection range of sweat biomarkers in synthetic sweat samples by gold standard tests and comparison of detection carried out using flexible biosensor patch device using same samples.

Analyte	Linear regression analysis	
		Detection range
Glucose	Gold standard assay	0.6–2 mM
	Wearable sensor patch signal	0.01–1.0 mM
Ca ²⁺ ions	Gold standard assay	0.25–1.5 mM
	Wearable sensor patch signal	0.25–3.0 mM
IL-6	Gold standard assay	10–400 pg/mL
	Wearable sensor patch signal	10–300 pg/mL

state and provides insights into the interplay between immune activation and metabolic stress.

This work establishes a promising foundation for next-generation wearable bioelectronics that can assess inflammation, metabolic activity, and electrolyte balance in a more integrated manner. Although minor batch-to-batch variability and long-term receptor stability remain challenges, these may be addressed through standardized fabrication protocols and improved surface chemistries. Future works should focus on wireless and battery-free operation, sweat-rate-independent sensing, enhanced antifouling strategies, and systematic on-body clinical evaluation. Collectively, the results highlight the potential of this platform for real-time personalized health monitoring and translation toward practical wearable diagnostic systems.

4 | Experimental Section

4.1 | Characterizations

The morphology and elemental analysis of sample was carried out using SEM and energy dispersive spectroscopy with LEO Supra 35VP scanning electron microscope operated at 3 kV. UV-visible and Raman spectroscopy analysis was performed using a NanoDrop and Renishaw inVia Reflex Raman Microscope, respectively. FTIR measurements were performed using a Nicolet iS10 FTIR Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA) (4 cm⁻¹ resolution). XRD analysis was carried out on Bruker D8 DISCOVER X-ray diffractometer (Bruker AXS GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) with Cu target using scintillation counter ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV in the range of $2\theta = 10^\circ\text{--}70^\circ$. TGA of the polyimide (PI) substrate and graphene spin-coated substrates was analyzed by TGA analyzer (NETZSCH STA 449 C thermo-microbalance with TG resolution of 0.1 μg) from 25°C to 800°C at 10°C/min under N₂ flow of 20 mL/min.

4.2 | Design and Fabrication of Micro/Nano-Structured Graphene Interfaced Electrode Sensor Arrays on a Flexible Substrate and Optimization

Design and fabrication of wearable graphene interfaced electrochemical sensor patch was carried out on a flexible polymeric

substrate by using standard photolithography in a Class 100 cleanroom facility using polyimide (PI) as substrate by following steps.

4.2.1 | Coating graphene nanosheets on PI through spin coating and physico-chemical characterization

Step 1: Synthesis of graphene: Graphene oxide (GO) was first generated by chemical exfoliation of graphite to synthesize graphene using a previously described method by chemical reduction [33]. Briefly, 3 g of graphite and 15 g of KMnO₄ (99.35%) was mixed and carefully added into a mixture of 115 mL of sulfuric acid and nitric acid (1:3) while continuous stirring on ice-water bath (4°C) in a span of 2 h interval. The resulting mixture tended to change in its color from black to dark green. This mixture was then kept stirring for 24 h on a magnetic stirrer at a room temperature to obtain purple pasty material. Then 500 mL DI water was added slowly spanning an interval of 90 min at room temperature. Then the beaker was placed in a water bath at 98°C for 15 min to complete the reaction, and this was followed by addition of 500 mL of water and 50 mL of H₂O₂ (30%–35%) to the mixture, which turned the color of the solution from dark brown to yellow. The resulting solution was homogenized with proper mixing for 30 min in an ultrasonic bath. The solution was then filtered through a filter paper and the residue left behind on the filter paper was collected. This sample residue was divided into two parts and stirred by adding 500 mL of 2 M HCl for 1 h on a magnetic stirrer followed by washing each part with 500 mL distilled water. The solution was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 40 min and the supernatant was removed, and thus obtained GO pellet was resuspended in fresh DI water and the above cycle process was repeated several times until the sample showed its pH = 5. The GO sample was then purified by washing twice with ethanol and precipitated. The precipitated GO was again dispersed in DI water in 50 mL centrifuged tubes, frozen at -80°C then dried at 60°C for 48 h under vacuum. Finally, the pure GO was characterized by XRD and Raman techniques and stored until use.

Step 2: Synthesis of graphene from GO: As-synthesized GO from Step (1) was subjected to chemical conversion to graphene by reducing with ascorbic acid as a reducing agent. Briefly, 5 mg GO was added to 50 mL DI water and exfoliation of GO was achieved by ultrasonic dispersion. Then 50 mg of ascorbic acid was added to

50 mL of an aqueous dispersion of the GO under vigorous stirring. The pH of the suspension was adjusted to 10 by adding 3 M NH_4OH (3 mL) solution dropwise to promote colloidal stability through the electrostatic repulsion. Then the solution was stirred for 4 h at 70°C that changed the solution color from brown to black. The above mixture was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 30 min then washed with DI water and the process was repeated thrice to finally obtain the precipitated rGO, which was dried at 60°C in an oven.

As synthesized graphene sample was characterized by XRD and Raman spectroscopy. From the XRD analysis, the absence of peak at $2\theta \sim 26.5^\circ$ and appearance of new peak at $2\theta \sim 9.6^\circ$ indicates the conversion of graphite to GO completely (Figure S10(a)). As-synthesized GO was subjected to chemical conversion to reduced graphene by treating with ascorbic acid and characterized by Raman spectra (Figure S10). Notable differences were observed in Raman shift characteristics, where graphite showed its three characteristic peaks at 2718, 1580, and 1349 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the 2D, G, and D bands, respectively. The relatively minor intensity of the D peak, indicative of low disorder, suggests minimal defects on the graphite substrate. In contrast, pronounced D peaks observed in synthesized GO and rGO samples suggest significant disorder resulting from vigorous oxidative treatment during the graphite oxidation process. The transformation from GO to rGO was evident in the Raman spectra, with the G band shifting from 1580 to 1592 cm^{-1} , and a broadened D band at around 1325 cm^{-1} , reflecting reduced in plane sp^2 domain size due to extensive reduction.

After successful synthesis of graphene, this graphene was coated on PI substrates by spin coating method as follows: first PI substrate was treated with 0.1% sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS) and 0.1% sodium carbonate (w/w) for 30 min at 100°C and cleaned with distilled water and dried at 60°C . The polymeric substrates were further cleaned by UV-Ozone treatment for 30 min using ProCleaner Plus. For better adherence of graphene on PI, cleaned PI substrate was immersed into a poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate) (PSS) solution (3 mg/mL in 0.5 M NaCl) for 20 min followed by rinsing with DI water and dried under N_2 flow. PSS-coated PI was then immersed into polyethyleneimine (PEI) solution (3.5 mg/mL in 0.5 M NaCl) for 20 min and then rinsed with DI water and dried under N_2 flow. The PSS-PEI treated PI substrate was subjected to spin coating of graphene (0.5 mg/mL) at 3000 rpm, 30 s cycle for five cycles to generate 5 layers of graphene. Graphene-coated PI was then subjected to curing at 200°C in a vacuum oven and the final sample was characterized by XRD, Raman, TGA, and SEM imaging. Structural features, durability and stability of graphene-coated polymeric substrates were carried out by SEM imaging before and after several washing cycles (25–50). For this, each $3 \times 3\text{ cm}^2$ graphene-coated substrate was washed with a 200 mL of SDBS (0.37%) without optical brightener (WOB) solution in a 500 mL beaker containing 10 steel balls with a diameter of 6 mm at 40°C for 45 min similar to a previously reported method in accordance with the American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists (AATCC) testing method 61-2013 [25]. After successful confirmation of the durability and stability, the graphene-coated polymeric substrate was subjected to fabrication of graphene interfaced electrode by photolithography method and the details are described below:

4.2.2 | Patterning of micro/nano-structured graphene electrode sensor arrays on graphene-coated flexible PI substrates and mechanical integrity performance

Graphene-coated flexible PI substrates from the above Section (4.2.1) were subjected to patterning with gold microelectrodes to give rise to graphene interfaced array of sensors (electrical chip-based patch) using standard photolithography method. Here, the substrate surface was first cleaned and dried using N_2 gas. An image reversal mask patterning was carried out using a photoresist after layering it on substrate followed by baking process. A 10–12 nm thin titanium layer was deposited to facilitate improved adhesion of gold and a 150–170 nm thick gold layer deposited using direct current sputter deposition. The deposition was carried out in an argon atmosphere with optimized power (150–200 W) for 1–3 min. The metal was lifted off using acetone/ion etching procedure. The width of microelectrodes (graphene/gold) varied between 40 and $50\ \mu\text{m}$ with a same gap between the two electrodes for each sensor ($\sim 7\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm}$ area) (Figure S1). In the fabricated design of graphene interfaced electrochemical sensor arrays, the micro/nano-structured graphene interdigitated electrodes served as a working and two Au electrodes on either side as counter electrodes and reference electrodes all on PI patch substrate. To interpret the changes in sensor responses, the micro-nano-electrodes were also patterned on bare polymeric substrates with no graphene as controls (control sensor). The fabricated micro/nano-structured graphene interfaced electrochemical sensor arrays were characterized for its integrity and suitability for wearable patch sensor by optical/SEM imaging and photographic images. The mechanical resiliency of the fabricated sensor patch was tested against continuous applied mechanical stresses, such as stretching–relaxing, bending, twisting, and marking indentation that were recorded as photographic images for analysis. The present sensor patch design fabrication is not limited only to a photolithography process, but it can also be fabricated using different methods, including electron beam lithography, high-resolution laser-jet and ink-jet printing, screen printing, and roll-to-roll printing.

Here, the polymeric film substrate is not only restricted to PI, but also other flexible and stretchable substrates can be used including other polymers, such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET), silicone polymers, polyurethane, or cellulose-based papers. Within the circular design shape of the metal/graphene interdigitated sensor electrodes, the selection of conductive carbon nanomaterials includes graphene and its derivatives, single-/multi-walled carbon nanotubes. The metal microelectrodes are not limited to gold, but also applicable to other metals, such as platinum, palladium, silver, copper, nickel, or aluminum.

4.3 | Bio-Functionalization of Sensor Patch with Specific Chemical/Bioreceptor to Sweat Biomarker and Characterization

4.3.1 | Bio-functionalization of primary antibodies specific to sweat inflammatory biomarker and characterization

Bio-functionalization of antibody specific to sweat inflammatory/chronic diseases cytokine biomarkers, such as IL-6 was

carried out using covalent coupling method through crosslinking IL-6 antibodies with 1-pyrenebutanoic acid succinimidyl ester (PASE) on graphene and mercaptopropionic acid (MPA) on interdigitated gold electrodes. First, gold electrode arrays were cleaned and treated with 20 mM of MPA in methanol for 2 h to generate free $-\text{COOH}$ groups. The activated sensor patch was washed with pure methanol followed by water and dried. Then, graphene electrode arrays were treated with 5 mM of PASE for 2 h to generate a free NHS-ester groups. Freshly prepared 200 mM of 1-ethyl-3(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and 100 mM of *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) reaction mixture was incubated on sensor patch. The activated sensor patch was then incubated overnight with 20 μL of anti-IL-6 antibodies (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) at 4°C. The sensor patch was thoroughly rinsed thrice with PBS solution (pH 7.4). Finally, the antibody immobilized sensor patch was incubated with 5% BSA in PBS solution to block free or unreacted functional groups on sensor patch. Detection of IL-6 in a window of 0.1–300 pg/mL in synthetic sweat, specificity and selectivity of the sensors were carried out.

4.3.2 | Bio-functionalization of glucose oxidase enzyme on fabricated graphene patch and characterization

For glucose sweat biomarker sensing, the capture probe IgG monoclonal antibody specific to glucose oxidase enzyme was functionalized on cleaned graphene interdigitated electrodes arrays by chemical cross-linking chemistry using a modified method previously reported [8, 28]. First, gold electrode arrays of sensor patch were cleaned and treated with 20 mM of MPA in methanol for 2 h to generate free $-\text{COOH}$ group. The activated sensor patch was washed with methanol followed by water and dried. The graphene interdigitated electrodes arrays were treated with 5 mM of PASE. Freshly prepared 200 mM of EDC and 100 mM of NHS reaction mixture was incubated on sensor patch. The PASE and EDC/NHS-activated sensors were coupled with α -glucose oxidase specific IgG antibody (5–10 μL of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and incubated for 15–20 min. The electrode arrays were thoroughly washed with aqueous solution. Glucose oxidase (GOx) enzyme solution (5 mg/mL) in PBS (pH 7.4) was then incubated on sensor at 4°C for 5 h and washed with PBS, pH 7.4 and stored at 4°C. Electron mediators, such as either 5 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ or Prussian blue (2.5 mM FeCl_3 , 100 mM KCl, 2.5 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, and 100 mM HCl) can be directly mixed with GOx. The antibody immobilized on sensor was confirmed by FTIR analysis. Detection of glucose was optimized to a concentration range 10 μM –1 mM in synthetic sweat and the specificity and selectivity were carried out.

4.3.3 | Chemical-functionalization of Ca^{2+} -ion selective membrane (Ca-ISM) on graphene patch and characterization

For selective sweat Ca^{2+} ion sensing, the surface modification of graphene electrochemical sensor was carried out with a calcium ion selective membrane (ISM) cocktail using a simple and easy ion-selective electrode (SC-ISE) solid-contact method. For this, Ca^{2+} ISM (Ca-ISM) cocktail was prepared using the following composition containing 1.0% (w/w) calcium ionophore *N,N,N',N'*-tetracyclohexyl-3-oxapentanediamide (ETH 129), 0.2%

(w/w) potassium tetrakis[3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]borate (KTFPB), 65.8% (w/w) *o*-nitrophenyl octyl ether (*o*-NPOE), and 33.0% (w/w) poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (THF) solvent [34]. For the surface modification of graphene sensor, Ca-ISM, 100 μL of cocktail deposited onto the working graphene electrode arrays surface. The functionalization of Ca-ISM on sensor surface was confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy.

4.4 | Electrochemical signal generation from sweat sensor patch

The cyclic voltammetry (CV) responses of sensor were measured using a handheld potentiostat by applying potential of -0.1 to $+0.1$ V and measured the signal as a function of current change (μAmp) with synthetic sweat for many cycles. Sensor calibration response was analyzed using several replicates ($n = 3-4$) and statistical errors were calculated.

4.4.1 | Stability, reproducibility, and statistical analysis

All experiments were carried out in biological and/or technical replicates ($n = 3-4$), and the average and standard deviation (SD) values were used for plotting. The inter and intra assay coefficient of variations (%CV) were calculated, and the results that showed below 10% CV were only considered qualified. Long-term stability of sensor patch was evaluated by measuring its electrochemical performance over time (after 1, 4, and 7 days).

4.4.2 | Variation in pH for glucose sensing

The fabricated sensor patch with a specific concentration of glucose was tested at varying pH of 6.4–7.4, and these pH values are close to the physiological pH of sweat samples.

4.4.3 | Repeatability and reproducibility

The sensors patch was tested in a successive repetition with appropriate concentration/s of selected sweat biomarker/s in artificial sweat and relative standard deviation (RSD%) was calculated. The reproducibility of sensor patch performance was evaluated by replicating electrochemical signal measurements ($n = 3-4$) with different fabricated electrochemical sensors arrays. The results that showed $\text{RSD} = \leq 5\%$ –10% were only regarded as valid data and those exceed over 10% were not considered valid in this work.

4.5 | Fabrication of artificial skin and setup for on-artificial skin testing

For this, artificial skin was fabricated by using a previously reported method [35, 36]. Briefly, 0.3267 g NaCl and 1.743 g agar mixed well in 56.25 g DI water. Here, NaCl adjusts conductivity and physiological salinity, while agar provides skin-like texture self-shaping and prevents water from evaporating. The mixture was then heated on a hotplate under slow stirring and removed

after observing an appropriate increase in viscosity. Following this step, 5.625 g PET powder and 1.382 g TX-151 were mixed and added to maintain the viscosity of agar and PET powder mixture and mixed thoroughly. The mixture is then transferred into a glass petri dish to obtain fabricated skin phantom. Pilot experiments were undertaken for the detection of known specific spiked concentration (0.1–0.6 mM) of model sweat biomarkers on artificial skin setup. The influence of skin temperature on sensor patch for sweat biomarkers detection was tested by measuring CV signal at a potential range -0.1 to 0.1 V with a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} from 25°C to 35°C .

4.6 | Design and Integration of Microfluidics and Sensor Arrays Patch

First, a microfluidic design layout suitable for patterning μ channels on sensor patch was drawn with the help of AutoCAD and printed high-resolution opaque black ink on an acetate mask. This mask was used as a template on silicon wafer for patterning microfluidic channels using SU8-2050 resin using photolithography. About 1.0 mL of SU8-2050 resin was dispensed on silicon substrate and programmed to coat in a two-step process, (i) by spin coating at 500 rpm for 15 s with an acceleration of 100 rpm/s, and (ii) at 1000 rpm for 30 s with an acceleration of 300 rpm/s. The wafer was then subjected to soft baking at 65°C for 7 min followed by 95°C for 30 – 45 min (hard baking at 65°C for 5 min followed by 95°C for 12 – 15 min). The wafer was removed and cooled for 10 min at room temperature and the wafer with thin polymer coating was subjected to UV-exposure using a template acetate mask in a mask-aligner (Midas). The UV exposure time, energy/power required was calculated using equation $E = \text{time} \times \text{power}$, where power = 14.7 J, energy density for 170 – 225 μm thickness = 260 – 350 mJ/m^2 . This process was optimized to yield microfluidic channel thickness of 170 – 220 μm . Finally, the SU8 mold was developed in a SU8 developer until clear μ channels appeared on the wafer and washed with isopropanol and dried.

This mold was placed in a clean Petri dish and the Slygard 184 silicone elastomer and hardener mixture (10:1 ratio) was poured until the mold was fully submerged. The entire content was placed under a vacuum desiccator to remove all the air bubbles. The Petri dish contents were later placed in a hot-air oven for curing at 75°C for 1 h. The cured silicone (polydimethylsiloxane, PDMS) layer was peeled out of the mold that left the microfluidic design imprints on PDMS. This layer was subjected to bonding on to a sensor patch made of PI film carrying pre-patterned metal-graphene microelectrodes. Before assembling the microfluidic device on sensor patch, the sensor patch was first affixed on a clean glass support and treated with 15 s Corona plasma treatment on both the surface of patch and silicone imprints that were overlaid and firmly clamped. The entire assembly was immediately placed in an oven overnight at 90°C for the thermal adhesion fusion bonding between the substrate and microfluidics mold for the adhesion of microfluidics pattern onto the sensor patch.

To facilitate the absorption of excess sweat, a thin absorbent rayon pad is positioned at the punctured outlet chamber of

the microfluidics module where the sample is collected. This accelerates the sweat absorption or the flow of the sweat sample through the sensor patch. Alternatively, if there is collected sweat in the inlet reservoir, it was manually driven through the sensor by compressing the closed-inlet reservoir chamber with a thumb, allowing the excess sweat to drain thorough the open outlet chamber.

4.6.1 | Microfluidic Platform Integrated Patch Sensor Performance

First, the sweat flow through the microfluidic channels on the sensors were characterized using a PBS solution. The flow rate experiments were performed using a syringe pump apparatus at a constant sweat rate of 15 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The thermal adhesion fusion bonding method applied for bonding substrate and microfluidics mold was tested for possible evaporation, which was assessed using a dye fluid in the microfluidic channel at different temperatures (25°C – 40°C) and relative humidity (RH%) rates over specific time intervals. Here, the degree of evaporation of fluid in the microfluidic channel was determined by the shifting of colored dye in the channel over a specific time interval (over ~ 60 min) and the results were analyzed.

4.6.2 | Signal-Read Out and Signal Processing Unit to Test Microfluidic Integrated Sensors Arrays for Off-Body/On-Artificial Skin Sweat Sensing Analysis

Sensor electrodes extending from the patch were connected through a customized adaptor to either a portable $\mu\text{Stat-i}$ 400 (Bi) potentiostat (DropSens), or a portable handheld adaptor unit of a EmStat Pico module (Analog Devices), controlled by a PSTouch Android smartphone application. This application facilitated signal-read out, signal processing and display output on a smartphone for all experiments conducted using fully integrated sensors arrays on flexible patch. All the volunteers have given informed consent to the experiments. According to the relevant regional regulations, the characterizations conducted were in vitro, non-clinical, and non-toxic, primarily intended for research on wearable devices. Formal approval from institutional authorities was not required.

4.7 | Sample Preparation for Fully Integrated Electrochemical Sensing Patch, Testing for Targeted Sweat Analytes/Biomarkers and Validation

4.7.1 | Sample preparation for the measurement of selected cytokine sweat biomarker (IL-6) in artificial sweat on graphene sensor patch and its specificity

Typically, IL-6 concentrations in human sweat varies from 5 to 15 pg/mL [37, 38]. Therefore, IL-6 biomarker concentrations were prepared at a range 0.1 – 300 pg/mL , which represents below normal to elevated/diseased levels. The samples were tested by serially dispensing in 10 – 30 μL volumes onto the sensor patch with increasing concentration gradient from 0.1 to 300 pg/mL followed by incubation for 15 – 20 min. Electrochemical parameters of IL-6 binding on sensors were measured and the

specificity of sensors was tested with non-specific molecules (negative control/s), such as bovine serum albumin (50 pg/mL) and glucose (50, 100 pg/mL). All the above non-specific molecules were tested on anti-IL6 functionalized graphene sensor surface for specificity performance.

4.7.2 | Sample preparation for measurement of glucose in synthetic sweat on graphene sensor patch and specificity

Artificial sweat samples containing varying glucose concentrations were prepared from lower 10 μM to a maximum 1 mM, which is a typical glucose concentration range reported in human sweat [39]. Different concentrations of glucose (in 10–30 μL) were dispensed and incubated for 15 min on the sensor surfaces prior to measuring electrochemical parameters. The selectivity of glucose sensing was carried out by testing them in the presence of other non-specific biomolecules (negative controls), such as fructose and uric acid.

4.7.3 | Sample preparation for Ca^{2+} in synthetic sweat and evaluation/measurement on graphene sensor patch and specificity

The graphene electrochemical patch sensor was tested against varying Ca^{2+} ions (0.25–3 mM) in 10 mM acetate buffer (pH 4.6). Here, Ca^{2+} ions concentration range is chosen from 0.1 to 1.5 mM and the Ca^{2+} levels body fluids commonly vary between 0.5 and 3 mM including sweat samples [40, 41]. Kinetic parameters for dynamic electrochemical response with Ca^{2+} were carried by exposing low/high concentrations of Ca^{2+} ions. The interference of other cations were tested, such as by addition of chloride forms of Mg^{2+} (1 mM), and K^+ (8 mM) ions. Electrochemical measurements were done within a 1 min waiting period window, and paused while changing solutions.

4.7.4 | Signal capturing for detection of model sweat biomarkers on sensor patch

The electrochemical kinetic signals/parameters (CV) were measured at potential range -0.1 to 0.1 V at scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} before and after the incubation of known concentrations of model sweat biomarkers (IL-6, glucose, and Ca^{2+}) in synthetic sweat on sensor patch. First, the CV response was measured sequentially as follows; (1) testing sensors immobilized with specific receptor elements (anti-IL antibodies, anti-glucose oxidase, and Ca-ISM), and (2) sensors incubated with varying levels of sweat biomarkers, specifically IL-6 (0.1–300 pg/mL), glucose (10 μM –1 mM), and Ca^{2+} ions (0.25–1.5 mM), respectively. The signal responses from sensor patch were measured using a portable Bi-potentiostat. The results of above step (1) were considered as zero-dose/baseline response for determining the sensor signals from specific biomarkers. Sensor responses were calibrated by considering replicate test sample measurements ($n = 3$ –4) along with positive and negative controls and statistically validated the sensor responses.

4.7.5 | Determining lower detection limit

The LoD for each specific lowest sweat biomarker concentration (IL-6, glucose, Ca^{2+}) was calculated using previously reported method [42]. The sensor response for spiked sweat biomarkers in synthetic sweat was fitted using polynomial curve fitting and regression analysis coefficient (R^2) were determined.

4.7.6 | Validation: Assay validation of biosensor patch for single/multiplexed detection using gold standard assays

Validation of model synthetic sweat using gold standard methods

The validation of Ca^{2+} ions in model synthetic sweat using Fluo-4 Direct Calcium Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) as a gold standard method. Here first, 2X Fluo-4 Direct calcium reagent loading solution (50 μL) was added to each well of a black 96-well microplate with transparent bottom and mixed with 50 μL of each test Ca^{2+} ions samples (0.25–3 mM) in synthetic sweat that were used for sensor patch testing. The plate was incubated at 37°C for 60 min under constant shaking and measured the fluorescence using a 485 nm excitation filter and 528 nm emission filter using Synergy HTX-multimode microplate reader (Biotek). For IL-6, an in house developed IL-6 ELISA kit was used as a gold standard assay for validating IL-6 levels in the synthetic sweat used for sensor patch measurements. Validation of patch sensor with synthetic sweat sample was tested using glucometer tests with Accu Chek Performa Nano Roche Glucose Meter (4015630066063) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Here, synthetic sweat sample containing different concentrations of glucose from 10 μM to 1 mM were prepared. First the glucose strip is inserted in the glucose meter and a glucose-baseline was established. The edge of the sensor strip was loaded with a 10 μL sample drop and read the glucose level (mg/dL) reading on display. For each tested glucose concentration, a new activation strip was used to read the glucose level.

4.8 | Practical Considerations and Translational Outlook

To evaluate the practical applicability of the developed platform, analytical performance assessment using real samples and repeated measurement cycles is currently underway to validate robustness and reproducibility. Efforts are also directed toward reducing fabrication costs without compromising sensing accuracy or material quality, which is critical for large-scale deployment. To improve wearability and enable fully autonomous operation, we have initiated integration of wireless power transmission for a battery-free sensor patch, along with wireless remote sensing capability. A miniaturized readout unit has been incorporated into a bandage-format wearable prototype (see Video S4), significantly improving user comfort and form factor. Furthermore, development of a web-based and smartphone application for real-time signal acquisition, processing, and conditioning is in progress. While the current system remains in a modular configuration, ongoing work focuses on complete

device integration toward a fully functional prototype suitable for real-world applications and commercial translation.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: admt70991-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.

Supporting File 2: admt70991-sup-0002-VideoCaption.docx.

Supporting File 3: admt70991-sup-0003-VideoS1-S4.zip.